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Liver Cirrhosis of HDV Etiology: Clinical and Laboratory Aspects

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Abstract. *The article presents the relevance of the problem of viral hepatitis D. The peculiarity of the course of chronic hepatitis D is, as a rule, a rapidly progressive course with the steady development of liver cirrhosis. The development of severe complications and the high frequency of disability of patients causes the necessity of studying the specific features of the course of LC. We have conducted a complex*

clinical and laboratory examination of seventy patients with LC, 37 of them with LC of HDV etiology and 33 with LC of HBV. Clinical signs of LC HDV etiology are extremely variable. It was found that LC can run with minimal signs, which makes their timely diagnosis difficult. In LC of class A, the main symptoms of the disease differed slightly between HBV and HDV infection. In LC of HDV etiology, fatigue, flatulence, and such manifestations as spleen enlargement, presence of collaterals, and palmar erythema were significantly more frequent. In LC HBV as well as in LC HDV, the Child-Pugh class B, the symptoms occurred with almost equal frequency. There were almost no differences in clinical manifestations, although ascites, collaterals, and palmar erythema were more frequently observed in HDV LC. However, the difference was not significant. The enzyme activity and the degree of dysproteinaemia did not depend much on the etiology of the disease but tended to increase with the severity of the pathological process.

Key words: HDV, HBV, liver cirrhosis, clinical picture, laboratory parameters

Introduction. Hepatitis delta virus (HDV), which is a satellite virus and exhibits its pathogenic effects only in the presence of hepatitis B virus (HBV), is associated with the most severe and unfavorable liver damage, with frequent outcomes in cirrhosis and hepatocellular carcinoma. According to published data, about 5% of chronic HBV carriers are co-infected with HDV [1] (As a result, approximately 15-20 million people around the world are HDV subscribers [2].

Chronic HBV and HDV coinfection is the most severe form of viral hepatitis, which has a much higher risk of liver cirrhosis and HCC than HBV monoinfection [3]. The peculiarity of the course of chronic hepatitis D is, as a rule, a rapidly progressive course with the steady development of liver cirrhosis in almost 60-80% of cases (Rizzetto M., 2000). The need to study the peculiarities of the course of LC is due to the development of severe complications and a high incidence of disability in patients. It is important to note that in more than 50% of patients, manifestation of

the disease may occur at the stage of decompensation, the presence of which indicates an unfavorable prognosis of the disease, when in more than 70% of patients, liver transplantation is considered as the only method of treatment. Thus, more rapid development of liver cirrhosis is observed in the outcome of chronic viral hepatitis D (CVHD) than in chronic hepatitis B. CVCD is the most severe form of chronic viral hepatitis, life-threatening for patients, characterized by a predominantly progressive course with a significantly (in 15% of patients within 1-2 years, in 70% of patients - within 5-10 years) higher mortality from liver failure (5- and 10-year survival rates in 49% and 40%, respectively), a significantly higher risk of hepatocellular carcinoma (3-6 times), liver transplantation (2 times), and death (2 times) compared to CVHB. Patients more often do not survive to develop HCC and die from complications of LC [4]. A mild course of CVHD with slower progression is relatively uncommon (10-15%).

The hidden (latent) hepatitis D is characterized by the detection of markers of active HBV replication only in liver tissue (HBV RNA, HDAg), while HDVAb may be detected in serum in the absence of HBsAg and HBV DNA (first described in patients undergoing orthotopic liver transplantation) [5]. Diagnosis requires a strong knowledge of the clinical manifestations of hepatitis delta.

Considering the relevance of the problem, our research aimed to study the clinical manifestations of different severities of the pathological process (according to Child-Pugh) of HDV LC in comparison with mono HBV LC.

Material and methods of research.

The object of the study was seventy patients with LC, 37 of them with LC HDV etiology and 33 with LC HBV etiology. The average age was $48.7 \pm 5.6\%$ and 36.2 ± 2.8 years, respectively. The distribution of patients by severity of pathological process was as follows: in LC HBV etiology-18 (54,5%) patients were classified as class A, class B - 14 (42,4%), class C - 1 (3,0%) patient. In HDV LC, 15 (40.5%) patients were classified as class A, 19 (51.3%) as class B, and 3 (8.1%) as class C.

General clinical examination methods:

Clinical manifestations were studied among patients with LC of B and D etiology who were under observation in our clinic.

Biochemical research methods.

All patients at the moment of admission, then regularly after 3 months, underwent conventional clinical methods of investigation, consisting of general blood and urine analysis and biochemical blood tests. Determination of hepatic process activity and assessment of disease severity included biochemical markers such as ALT, AST, GGT, alkaline phosphatase, bilirubin, serum albumin, globulins, blood coagulation, creatinine, and protein metabolism indices. Biochemical parameters were expressed in the international system of SI units.

Serological research methods.

The etiological diagnosis was established based on enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) results. Diagnostic kits (Nizhny Novgorod) for the detection of HBsAg, antibodies to HDV, and HCV in blood serum were used as test systems.

Molecular biological methods included PCR of blood to determine HBV DNA, HDV RNA, and viral load. We used the AmpliSens test systems.

Инструментальные методы исследования.

The main instrumental method of the study was an ultrasound examination of the liver, gallbladder, and spleen using a Haiying device manufactured in China. Elastography of the liver was performed using FibroScan 402 and 502 (Echosens, France).

Statistical analysis of the results was conducted with an assessment of the statistical significance of differences between comparable values using Student's criterion. Differences were considered reliable at $P < 0.05$.

The study's results A comprehensive clinical and laboratory examination of seventy patients with LC was conducted. Thirty-seven of them had LC of HDV etiology. There were 20 (54.1%) men and 17 (45.9%) women. Thirty-three patients with LC of

HBV etiology: men—18 (54.5%), women—15 (45.5%). CKD was slightly more frequently observed in males. The most frequent clinical manifestations included such general symptoms as weakness, rapid fatigability, reduced ability to work, abdominal discomfort, dyspeptic disorders, flatulence, weight loss, and nervous system asthenization (Table 1). Bleeding gums, right subcostal pain, abdominal pain, flatulence, and weight loss were frequently noted. On examination, most patients showed signs of liver failure - palmar erythema, collaterals. At palpation, there was an enlargement of the liver with thickening and deformation of the surface, sharpening of its edge with uniform enlargement of both liver lobes; later, the enlargement of the left lobe of the liver prevailed. Almost all patients showed enlargement of the spleen.

TABLE 1. Clinical symptoms of liver cirrhosis of HDV and HBV etiology

Symptoms	LC HDV (37)	LC HBV (33)
Weakness	35 (94,5%)	19 (57,5%)*
Fatigue	36 (97,2%)	25 (75,7%)*
Weight loss	20 (54,0%)	12 (36,3%)*
Headache	9 (24,3%)	7 (21,2%)
A decrease in appetite	10 (27,0%)	7 (21,2%)
Nausea	4 (10,8%)	2 (6,0%)
Bleeding gums	19 (51,3%)	14 (42,4%)
Itchy skin	4 (10,8%)	2 (6,0%)
Heaviness in the right hypochondrium	27 (72,9%)	23 (69,6%)
Abdominal pain	14 (37,8%)	11 (33,3%)
Ictericity of the sclera	25 (67,5%)	10 (30,3%)*
Swelling on the legs	4 (10,8%)	2 (6,0%)
Meteorism	29 (78,3%)	28 (84,8%)
Ascites	18 (48,6%)	15 (45,4%)
Palmar erythema	24 (64,8%)	18 (54,5%)
Spider veins	26 (70,2%)	19 (57,5%)
Collaterals	24 (64,8%)	13 (39,3%)
Dark urine	7 (18,9%)	14 (42,4%)
Stool discoloration	6 (16,2%)	4 (12,1%)
The liver's enlarged	17 (45,9%)	20 (60,6%)
The liver's shrunken	20 (54,0%)	12 (36,3%)
The spleen is enlarged	36 (97,2%)	31 (93,9%)

Note: *- Significant differences between the frequency of symptoms in HBV and HDV LC.

In Child-Pugh class B, there were external signs of liver failure - ascites, peripheral edema, and venous collaterals. Splenomegaly is often accompanied by hypersplenism and esophageal and gastric varices.

We have carried out a comparative analysis of some symptoms in LC of HDV and HBV etiology in different classes differing in severity of course and degree of functional insufficiency: in classes A and B, 33 patients each. In class A, the main symptoms of the disease differed slightly between HBV and HDV LC. Fig. 1 shows the most frequent symptoms in class A HBV and HDV LC.

Figure 1. The most common manifestations of LC of Child-Pugh class Child-Pugh class A for HBV and HDV

In LC HDV etiology, fatigue, flatulence, and manifestations such as enlarged spleen, the presence of collaterals, and palmar erythema were much more common. (Fig. 1 and 2 combine, weakness and fatigue and flatulence on top).

Figure 2. The most common manifestations of LC of Child-Pugh class B for HBV and HDV

In HBV and HDV LC of Child-Pugh classes B, symptoms were observed with almost equal frequency. The clinical manifestations had almost no differences. In patients with HDV LC class B, ascites (67.3% and 53.4%, respectively), collaterals (50.5% and 45.6%), and palmar erythema (42.5% and 39%) were more frequent than in HBV LC, but the difference was not significant. Ultrasound findings had non-significant differences in HBV and HDV LC. The liver was enlarged in 43.5% and 36.5%, respectively, and reduced in size in 30.2% and 20.3% of patients. The echo structure in all patients was not homogeneous. Echogenicity was increased, and parenchyma was thickened and heterogeneous. Peripheral vessels with reduced clarity. Intrahepatic bile ducts and vessels were dilated. Diameter of V. portae 15,1±1,2 mm and 13,8±1,4 (P>0,05), portae inferior 25,3±2,1 and 23,4±1,8 and mm (P>0,05), choledochus 3,7±1,0 and 3,1±1,5 mm (P>0,05). The spleen was enlarged in 100% and 68.5% (P<0.05), respectively.

Biochemical parameters were altered in the majority of patients. In more than half of the cases, there was an increase in blood bilirubin, the maximum values of which increased up to 185 µmol/l due to the direct fraction. Mean biochemical

parameters are presented in Table 3. In group comparisons, no significant differences in bilirubin indices were found; the difference was observed with increasing severity of the disease in both HBV ($P < 0.01$) and HDV ($P < 0.05$) infections. The degree of liver damage was assessed by the presence of cytolytic syndrome, manifested by the degree of severity of AlAT activity and other liver tests.

TABLE 2. Mean values of maximum biochemical parameters at different degrees of LC severity

Biochemicals shows	LC Class A		LC Class B		P1	P2
	HBV	HDV	HBV	HDV		
Bilirubin, $\mu\text{mol/l}$	28,9 \pm 4,8	32,5 \pm 3,2	48,7 \pm 3,1	56,8 \pm 4,1	$P < 0,05$	$P < 0,005$
ALAT, IU/ml	45,2 \pm 2,7	51,6 \pm 1,63	54,5 \pm 2,6	57,6 \pm 3,5	$P < 0,05$	$P > 0,05$
AST, IU/ml	37,4 \pm 4,3	42,4 \pm 2,5	47,3 \pm 3,4	49,1 \pm 3,8	$P > 0,05$	$P > 0,05$
Albumin, g/l	39,2 \pm 2,4	40,2 \pm 3,2	21,5 \pm 3,2	20,1 \pm 2,8	$P < 0,005$	$P < 0,005$
GTTP, un	57,6 \pm 2,3	61,5 \pm 3,8	62,3 \pm 3,2	84,5 \pm 5,3*	$P > 0,05$	$P < 0,01$
PTI, %	86,5 \pm 5,6	83,2 \pm 3,8	75,7 \pm 4,2	65,8 \pm 5,6	$P < 0,05$	$P < 0,05$

P1 – Significant differences between laboratory values in HBV class A and B LC.

P2 - Significant differences between laboratory values in Class A and B HDV LCs

As it can be seen from the table, the enzyme activity and the degree of dysproteinaemia did not depend much on the etiology of the disease. Moreover, the increase was associated with the severity of the pathological process. The fluctuations of AlAT activity in LC of different disease severities indicate that AlAT and AsAT did not always correspond to the severity of the course. At a severe course of LC of class C, according to Child-Pugh, the indices of AlAT decreased, which indicated extensive necrosis of hepatocytes. However, the activity of AsAT increased with the increasing severity of the process. That was an indicator of damage to other organs and systems as a result of the systemic nature of the disease. Significant differences had indicators of protein fractions and were characterized by a decrease in albumin

and PTI levels depending on the severity of the disease. Prothrombin index was reduced to 75.7% in HBV LC and to 65.8% in HDV LC ($P>0.05$).

Conclusions

- Thus, the clinical features of Hepatitis delta LC are highly variable. Diagnosis of this disease requires clear knowledge of the clinical manifestations.
- LC can run with minimal signs, which makes their timely diagnosis difficult.
- In class A LC, the main symptoms of the disease differed slightly between HBV and HDV infection. In HDV LC, fatigue, flatulence, and manifestations such as spleen enlargement, collaterals, and palmar erythema were more frequent.
- In HBV and HDV LV of Child-Pugh grades B, the symptoms occurred with almost equal frequency. Clinical manifestations had almost no differences, although ascites, collaterals, and palmar erythema were more frequently observed in HDV LC, and palmar erythema, but the difference was not significant.
- Enzyme activity and degree of dysproteinaemia had little dependence on the etiology of the disease. The increase was associated with the severity of the pathological process.

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